

ISSN: 2250-1258

Indian Journal of Ancient Studies and Linguistics

Volume: 14; Issue:2; 2024

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13723749>

The Evolution of Women's Status in Indian Society: A Historical and Cultural Perspective

Dr. Krishna Kant Sharma

Email: drkrishnakantsharma@gmail.com; M: 9504782781.

ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6009-3024>.

Abstract:

This paper examines the dynamic role of Indian societal structures in shaping the status of women from ancient to modern times. The research delves into the significant shifts in women's roles, influenced by various factors including the codification of social rules, religious doctrines, caste systems, and foreign invasions. The study highlights how these elements contributed to the deterioration of women's status, particularly during the Vedic and medieval periods. Additionally, it explores the intersection of gender with religious and cultural practices, demonstrating how these have both empowered and oppressed women across different eras. The analysis includes perspectives from various scholars on the implications of patriarchy, caste systems, and the socio-religious constructs that continue to affect women's rights and status in contemporary India. The paper underscores the need for a nuanced understanding of gender equality that considers historical, cultural, and social contexts to address ongoing discrimination and promote women's empowerment.

Keywords: Women Status in India; Evolution of Women in Indian Society; Indian Culture and Women.

For ages, the Indian societal structure has played an active role in stimulating the trends of change in women's status, which with time also proved to be a hindrance to the progress of this country. In a study, Bhaswati Pal has found that during the period 1500 BC to 647 AD, the deterioration in women's roles and position can be attributed to the imposition of Mānu's codification of social rules, gender-based discrimination, Brahmanical austerity applied to the entire Indian society, the crudest materialization of women, the implementation of rigid restrictions induced by the societal caste system and the system of joint families, women's exclusion from educational facilities, foreign invasions, as well as the introduction of non-Aryan females as wives in Aryan families. The study further disclosed that although Indian society has never accepted womanhood as being equal since the age of Dharmaśāstras, Mānasmṛiti, even today women's stories are reflected repeatedly as interesting episodes from the ancient period of Indian civilization (Pal, 2019). In another study, Dr. Neeta Khandelwal also found that there was no gender discrimination existed in the ancient period. Girls had equal privileges, in all spheres of life viz., education, marriage, employment, etc. However, in the medieval period, women were pushed downhill from the highest freedom and status due to the impact of Muslims, corruption vices like the purdah system, child marriage, etc. She further mentioned that in the modern era, despite several legislative regulations and acts, discrimination between men and women still exists due to the negative attitude of men towards women, and several other atrocities are being faced by women viz., dowry death, rape, prostitution, etc. (Khandelwal, 2016). Carol C. Mukhopadhyay studied that a major contribution of anthropology has been to expand the boundaries of current theorizing in our own and other academic disciplines through carrying out research in non-Western cultural contexts. He further mentioned that feminist cognitive anthropology can play this role in psychological and educational theorizing about gendered science and mathematics (Mukhopadhyay, 2004). Dr. Bir Pal Singh wrote that *the fight is not for women's status but for human worth. The claim is not to end the inequality of women but to restore universal justice. The bid is not for loaves and fishes for the forsaken gender but for cosmic harmony, which never comes until a woman comes* (Singh, 2013). Ujjayini Ray, after studying the ancient Hindu texts has summarized that *the status of a woman was superior as a mother compared to being a wife or a daughter* (Ray, 1999). A paper by Preeti S Rawat highlighted that the empowerment of women is linked to the belief and practice of patriarchy which subjugates women at various levels – political, economic, social, and cultural (Rawat, 2014). Keya Das and T. S. Sathyanarayana Rao have chronicled the conceptualization of sexuality in its inception in ancient India and its journey through the ages. They found that sexuality in India has undergone paradigm shifts from the Bronze Age civilization to present-day India. Ever-changing facets dependent on the cultural, social, religious, political, regional, and timely aura have resulted in sexuality in India having many hues. The manner of

experience and expression has also undergone significant changes over time in individual desires, attitudes to sex, beliefs, values, behaviors, gender roles, and relationships (Rao, 2019). Sexuality is constructed upon individuals' sexual orientation that is their emotional and sexual attraction to particular genders. Sexuality broadly encompasses the biological, physical, emotional, social, and spiritual aspects (Chakraborty K, 2013). In a paper, *Soumi Rai* tried to conceptualize Coontz's (2013) work on gender equality as no longer a women's issue but as an issue of looking beyond the gender lens and seeing employees' best qualities regardless of their gender in the Indian context (Rai, 2018). In their paper, *Chris Bidner* and *Mukesh Eswaran* have highlighted the gender aspect being responsible for endogamy being one of the features of the caste system. According to them, the restriction was also imposed on women to marry out of their caste to maintain their family income (Eswaran, 2014). A paper by *Chand R. Sirimanne* highlighted that gender equality from a Buddhist perspective is certainly not about blaming everything on men for they too are victims of stereotypical gender roles. From a materialistic and political point of view, this may still be a 'man's world' but when one looks at the statistics from almost every country, this seems a hollow claim (Sirimanne, 2016). In a paper, *Atasi Mahapatra* abstracted that in Vedic society women participated in religious ceremonies and tribal assemblies. Widows could remarry and child marriages were unknown in society. However, in the later Vedic period, the position of women gradually deteriorated. The period sees the growing tendency to stratify society along gender lines. Women lost their political rights. Child marriage, the system of Sati emerged in the shape of a formal custom during the later Vedic period. Nevertheless, in Buddhist and Jain culture women were accorded respect and their rightful place in society (Mahapatra, 2018). A paper by *Swati Sharma* highlighted the role played by culture and traditions specifically of the Hindu religion in legitimizing the subordinate position of women in Indian society. Along with presenting a brief account of the status of women from ancient times to contemporary situations, the sex-gender binary has also been explored. How a child after his birth socialized to behave in a certain way because of his/her sex has been noted. This process of socialization is based on the age-old customs and traditions which are discriminatory. The male child is taught to be strong, dominating, and aggressive and henceforth assigned laborious work to do for managing the finances of the house. On the other hand, the female child is taught to be sensitive, loving, and caring, and therefore assigned to manage household work, child nurturing, and motherhood-related responsibilities (Sharma, 2017). *Moirra Gatens* in a paper highlighted that in recent years it has become increasingly prevalent, in texts and papers concerned with sexual politics, to encounter the sex/gender distinction. The author also found that the distinction between sex and gender is used in both confusing and confusing ways (Kumari, Tandon, & Batra, 2017). According to *Archana Malik-Goure*, the issue of women is not just something metaphysical, it is a practical thing and everybody has their own experience of life. Not necessarily as an individual but as a member of the society (Malik-Goure, 2019). According to *Meena Bhati* women not only were the housemaids but also learned philosophers who have contributed to the religious quests of humanity. In the words of Manu Smiriti, 'woman is a perpetual minor and has to lead her entire life under the guardianship of the father, the husband or the son (Narayanan, 2016). *Caste hierarchy and gender hierarchy are the organizing principles of the Brahmanical social order and are closely interconnected. In an article, it was explored the relationship between caste and gender, and focused on what is possibly the central factor for the subordination of the upper caste woman: the need for effective sexual control over such women to maintain not only patrilineal succession but also caste purity in the institution unique to Hindu society* (EPW, 1993). Powerful instruments of religious and legal sanctions back the authority of men to dominate them. Therefore, for effective comprehension of the true nature and character of the evolutionary process of formulation of various social structures and institutions, it becomes imperative to identify such forces at work at various points in time (Gautam, 2014). A paper by *Meena A. Kelkar* attempted to evolve the possible perspective for making a particular type of classification and in the light of this perspective tries to elaborate the three models of man-woman relationship and suggest their implications for feminist theory (Kelkar, 1999). A paper by *Maitrayee Chaudhury* explores how the language of tradition and modernity has been the dominant idiom that has sought to capture the "essence" of both the Indian nation and the Indian woman. The salience of this discourse demands a critical inquiry to understand how this overarching and hegemonic idiom has been accepted as an unproblematic given (Chaudhury, 2012). Not only in India but also all over the world there has been a close link between feminism and the women's movement, each inspiring and enriching the other (Pande, 2018).

Jayasree K. Kuniyath and *Dr.K.C.Sankaranarayanan* abstracted that ideal women of India are appreciated based on their kulinisam and characters like fidelity, chastity, servitude towards her husband and his family, obeisance, non-fickle mind behavior, honesty, purity and many more. By fascinating and conditioning women based on these characteristics given by society, Indian masculine egotism made women dump driven cattle from womb to tump. For that, they used and made many ideals with the help of folkways, Epics, Puranas, and

smrithis. Myths and mythology have a big role in women's degradation in India and This paper focuses its attention on the position of India women-related mythology and the role of such myths in women's position degradation (Kuniyath & Dr.K.C.Sankaranarayanan, 2017). Carol S. Anderson et.al described in their book about How do gender constructions transform religious experiences?' 'What is the role of bodily materiality in ethics and epistemology?' 'How does rethinking gender and sexuality force us to reconceptualize settled ontological frameworks?' This collection provides the first research resource on Indian philosophical gender issues, exploring a variety of texts and traditions from Indian philosophy where the treatment of gender is dynamic and diverse (Anderson, Ashton, Balkaran, Maderey, & Gupta, 2019). According to Norris and Inglehart, the relation between religion and gender equality can be explained by the assertion that societies with higher religiosity accept the authority of religious teachers, who advocate a patriarchal organization of society. We assume that those women who adhere to the dominant religions, might also not be inclined to take part in their society's public life, due to their upbringing and the social traditions surrounding them. Nevertheless, many religious institutions are always helpful for women in economic and social distress (Inglehart, 2004).

Conclusion:

The evolution of women's status in Indian society reveals a complex interplay between cultural, religious, and societal forces that have both uplifted and suppressed women over time. While ancient Indian society offered women certain privileges and respect, particularly in religious and educational spheres, the subsequent periods saw a decline in their status due to rigid societal norms and patriarchal structures. The persistence of gender discrimination in modern times, despite legislative efforts, underscores the deep-rooted nature of these challenges. The study concludes that achieving true gender equality in India requires not only legal reforms but also a fundamental shift in societal attitudes and cultural practices. It calls for a re-examination of traditional norms and the promotion of an inclusive approach that values women's contributions across all domains of life. By addressing the historical and cultural contexts that have shaped gender roles, society can move towards a more equitable and just future for women.

References:

- Anderson, C. S., Ashton, G., Balkaran, D. R., Maderey, A. L., & Gupta, a. G. (2019). *Handbook of Indian Philosophy and Gender*. Bloomsbury Academic.
- Chakraborty K, T. R. (2013). Indian concepts on sexuality. *Indian J Psychiatry*, 55, 250-255.
- Chaudhury, M. (2012). Indian "Modernity" and "Tradition": A Gender Perspective. *Polish Sociological Review*, 2 (178)(12), 277-289.
- EPW. (1993). Conceptualizing Brahmanical Patriarchy in Early India. *EPW*, 28(14). Retrieved from <https://www.epw.in/journal/1993/14/special-articles/conceptualising-brahmanical-patriarchy-early-india-gender-caste>
- Eswaran, C. B. (2014). *A Gender-Based Theory of the Origin of the Caste System of India*. ASBSRG and SSHRC.
- Gautam, P. (2014). Understanding Past through Gender Perspective. *International Journal of Research in Humanities and Social Sciences*, 2(2), 41-44. Retrieved from www.rajmr.com
- Inglehart, N. a. (2004). *Sacred and secular: Religion and politics worldwide*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Kelkar, M. A. (1999). Man-Woman Relationship in Indian Philosophy. *Indian*, 71-87.
- Khandelwal, D. N. (2016). Gender sensitization among women in ancient India and their contemporary relevance. *International Journal of Home Science*, 2(3), 214-218. Retrieved from www.homesciencejournal.com
- Kumari, P. V., Tandon, P. U., & Batra, N. (2017). *Gender Justice and Feminist Jurisprudence*. New Delhi: Faculty of Law, University of Delhi.
- kuniyath, J. K., & Dr.K.C.Sankaranarayanan. (2017). Divine Gender Inequality: A Study of the Mythological Degradation of Hindu Woman in India. Retrieved from <https://ssrn.com/abstract=2949781>

Historical and cultural perspective of women status in India.

- Mahapatra, A. (2018). Gender equality and ancient Indian culture: A study. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science Invention (IJHSSI)*, 7(8), 22-26. Retrieved from www.ijhssi.org
- Malik-Goure, A. (2019). Feminist Philosophical Thoughts in Colonial India. *Journal of East-West Thought*, 25-36.
- Mukhopadhyay, C. C. (2004). A Feminist Cognitive Anthropology: The Case of Women and Mathematics. *Ethos*, 32(4), 458-492. Retrieved from <http://www.ucpress>
- Narayanan, S. (2016). Historical Background of Gender Equality and Succession Rights of Hindus. *Intellectual Property Rights*, 4(2). doi:10.4172/2375-4516.1000162
- Pal, B. (2019). The saga of women's status in ancient Indian civilization. *MISCELLANEA GEOGRAPHICA – REGIONAL STUDIES ON DEVELOPMENT*, 23(3), 180-184. doi:10.2478/grid-2019-0012
- Pande, R. (2018). The History of Feminism and Doing Gender in India. *Revista Estudos Feministas*, 26(3). doi:<https://doi.org/10.1590/1806-9584-2018v26n358567>
- Rai, S. (2018). Can We Look Beyond Gender Social Roles in Indian Management? *Teoria in Praksa*, 55(3), 518-541.
- Rao, K. D. (2019). A Chronicle of Sexuality in the Indian Subcontinent. *Journal of Psychosexual Health*, 1(1), 20-25. doi:10.1177/2631831818822017
- Rawat, P. S. (2014). Patriarchal Beliefs, Women's Empowerment, and General Well-being. *Vikalpa*, 39(2).
- Ray, U. (1999). Idealizing Motherhood: The Brahmanical Disclosure on Woman in Ancient India (Circa 500 BCE- 300 CE). *PhD Thesis Submitted to School of Oriental and African Studies, University of London*.
- Sharma, S. (2017). Relationship Between Culture And Gender Inequality In India. *IOSR Journal Of Humanities And Social Science (IOSR-JHSS)*, 22(10), 30-35. doi:10.9790/0837-2210063035
- Singh, D. B. (2013). Status of women in Vedic age. *Indian Society*, 22. Retrieved from <http://www.importantindia.com/2954/status-of-woman-in-vedic-age>
- Sirimanne, C. R. (2016). Buddhism and Women-The Dhamma Has No Gender. *Journal of International Women's Studies*, 18(1), 272-292. Retrieved from <http://vc.bridgew.edu/jiws/vol18/iss1/17>
